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*Feminist movements
revitalizing Democracy in Europe.*

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D7.1 Project Handbook & Management Plan

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FIERCE consortium

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5	BEN	SMART VENICE SRL	SV	IT
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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CR	Change Request
DL	Deliverable Leader
DoA	Description of the Action
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KR	Key Results
PC	Project Coordinator
QA	Quality Assurance
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SO	Specific Objectives
TBD	To Be Determined
ToC	Table of Content
TLs	Task Leaders
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
PMT	Project Management Team
PPB	Project Plenary Board
PC	Project Coordinator
QAM	Quality Assurance Manager
AB	Advisory Board
EA	Ethics Advisor

Executive Summary

The goal of this deliverable is to illustrate the project management framework of the FIERCE project along with all project quality control and operational procedures and associated roles required by the different managerial and operational activities planned for the whole project duration. This document is designed as a set of practical guidelines to help clearly define workflows and rules that the partners will have to follow throughout the project's activities, to ensure the highest quality standards are met and to strengthen project management (e.g., partner responsibilities, quality control mechanisms, documentation control, documentation formats and exchange rules).

The document lists the procedures required for a well-organised execution of the project, aiming to maximise cooperation of partners and to clearly define responsibilities among the beneficiaries of the project. Furthermore, the document clearly specifies the quality, administrative and communication procedures to be followed by the partners during the implementation of the project, to ensure full control of its development, from both a financial and a technical standpoint.

This report complements the provisions of the Grant Agreement and its annexes as well as the Consortium Agreement, which has been already signed by all the beneficiaries, in that it clearly defines several practical guidelines and rules essential for the day-to-day management of the project.

1. Introduction to the FIERCE Project

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender actors and discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2021. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, will be studied through frame analysis, political ethnography and Social Network Analysis on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. FIERCE will cover eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE moves beyond a country-based approach and provides a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics and output of the policy process. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. Description of WP7 – Project Management & Coordination

The main objective of this Work Package is:

- Coordinate decision making and conflict resolution.
- Handle the administrative and financial management of the project.
- Coordinate the Project and Scientific management of the project.
- Implement quality, innovation, and risk management, and to consider ethical and legal considerations during the project's implementation.

1.3. Introduction to the deliverable report – Document Scope

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a single point of reference on the management and quality that will be governed during the course of the project. It defines the project organisation, roles and responsibilities with emphasis on the quality control and quality assurance activities that will be carried out. It describes how the project will execute its day-to-day activities from a quality perspective and ensures that standards, processes, and procedures are defined, and their execution is continuously monitored and improved. A reference to all the necessary mechanisms and structures for the management and administrative coordination of the project capitalising on the governance, change management, communication plan, project calendar, stages, milestones, and reporting roles and responsibilities for all the partners is also made.

1.4. Document Structure

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

Chapter 1 presents an introduction to the project and the document. **Chapter 2** offers further project information, to provide the context for this document. **Chapter 3** explains the overall strategy and

approach towards managing the project including the management structure, partner roles and responsibilities, procedures, baselines, milestones and indicators. **Chapter 4** establishes the baseline performance of FIERCE in terms of schedule, resources, cost and overall quality. **Chapter 5** presents the quality management approach of FIERCE. **Chapter 6** presents the way the project will handle changes to the established plans and baselines. **Chapter 7** presents the communication flows, instruments and guidelines to the project. **Chapter 8** describes in brief the way the coordination team intends to manage costs and efforts. The two are placed in the same procedure as they are closely linked. **Chapter 9** documents the processes and techniques for the evaluation and control of potential project risks, focusing on their precautionary diagnosis and handling.

2. Project Context and Workplan

2.1. Project Scope and Outcomes

FIERCE aims to revitalize the alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers. These alliances have been pivotal in the past to bring feminist claims on the political agenda (i.e., state feminism concepts and practices). We envision the possibility to rekindle the movement-institution relationship by means of a multidimensional, bottom-up and impact-oriented approach.

Figure 1 - FIERCE Methodological Approach

FIERCE's strategic objectives

- Analysing and de-constructing the gender-binary rhetoric and frames disseminated by the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements, which inherently also fosters homo- and trans-phobic positions.
- Identifying discursive and consensus-seeking mechanisms through which the anti-feminist and anti-gender milieus gain traction among “like-minded”, and how these frames are appropriated by the public opinion.
- Analysing the complex constellation of alliances that promotes policy positions that are detrimental to gender equality and gender rights.
- Investigating the relationship between the contemporary democratic deficit, the spread of radical right populism in different national settings and the proliferation of anti-feminist, anti-gender positions.
- Building on a participatory research of the feminist movements to explore democratic alternatives and innovations as well as the strength and constraints of the intersectional approach experimented by the feminist movements.
- Studying the tensions and conflicts originating from opening up feminism to intersectional approaches and identifying discursive and practical tools to expand intersectional feminist dialogue and alliances.
- Utilizing a co-creative and participatory approach to research feminist activities and practices by creating national hubs of feminist movements and political actors from representative democratic institutions, jointly with a transnational EU level network.
- Generating knowledge and best practices that can have a transformative impact on democratic approaches and visions.

FIERCE aims at achieving its main objective by accomplishing the following specific objectives:

Table 1 - FIERCE Specific Objectives

Obj. Num	Objective description	WPs involved	Start	End	# of KPIs	KPIs	TARGET
Obj. 1	Understanding the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational level that explain the rise, mobilization patterns and alliance-building by the anti-feminist and anti-gender movements; this in the crisis-ridden decade 2010- 2021	WP1,WP2, WP3	M1	M36	1.1	A mapping of the actors, with timelines of most salient gender issues and debates IN EACH COUNTRY AND AT EU LEVEL , over the period 2010-21, catalogued according to a common matrix including five main thematic areas (labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; gender-based violence)	Mapping (National / EU level)
Obj. 2	Identifying how gender issues and debates are framed, communicated and disseminated by both feminist and anti-gender movements	WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	2.1	A content and frame analysis of a total minimum of forty (40) interviews (5 per country represented) with representatives from anti-gender movements	40 interviews (anti-gender repr.)
		WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	2.2	A content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 40 interviews with representatives from parties and policy decision makers/actors	40 interviews (policy makers)
		WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	2.2	A content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 80 parliamentary campaigns.	80 parliamentary campaigns
		WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	2.2	A content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 80 social media campaigns.	80 social media campaigns
		WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	2.3	A content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 160 document entries	160 document analysis
		WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	2.4	A content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 80 social media campaigns	80 social media campaigns analysis
Obj. 3	Mapping the constellation of actors involved in feminist and anti-gender movements, respectively, their	WP1, WP2, WP3	M1	M36	3.1	Content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 80 parliamentary debates.	80 parliamentary debates
		WP1, WP2, WP3			3.1	Content and frame analysis of a total minimum of 80 social media campaigns	80 social media campaigns

	relationship and connections with other relevant (external) actors and the policy influence on gender politics at institutional level.	WP1, WP2, WP3			3.2	SNA of >10 mln tweets from the 8 countries developed and analysed per country	SNA of >80 mln tweets
		WP1, WP2, WP3			3.2	2 Social Networks maps developed and analysed per country	16 Social Networks maps
Obj. 4	Exploring how feminist movements develop and foster concrete practices aimed at renewing forms of democratic participation and deliberation, and how they build upon intersectional alliances	WP2, WP3, WP4	M7	M26	4.1	A total minimum of 160 interviews with activists from feminist movements	160 interviews (feminist activists)
		WP2, WP3, WP4			4.2	A total minimum of 80 interviews with representatives from political parties or policy decision makers/actors	80 interviews (policy makers)
		WP2, WP3, WP4			4.3	A content and frame analysis of minimum total 160 parliamentary debates	160 parliamentary debates
		WP2, WP3, WP4	M7	M26	4.3	A content and frame analysis of minimum total 80 social media campaigns	80 social media debates
Obj. 5	Study causes and find solutions to the possible tensions among feminist organizations on intersectionality issues, which may prevent the formation of broader political alliances and weaken the political impact of feminism and its ability to counteract anti-gender rhetorics	WP2, WP3, WP4			5.1	Research and analysis of 8 Case Studies	Analysis of 8 case studies
		WP2, WP3, WP4	M9	M26	5.2	>160 participants of co-creation Labs (mixed composition of feminist movements and, organizations, party representatives and scholars)	>160 participants of co-creation Labs
		WP2, WP3, WP4	M9	M26	5.3	>24 National sessions over the 3 co-creation cycles	>24 National sessions
Obj. 6	Facilitating alliances within feminist movements and between feminist movements and different minority movements to contribute elaborating an intersectional approach to democratic	WP4, WP5	M9	M26	6.1	>160 participants to co-creation Labs (mixed composition of feminist movements and, organizations, party representatives and scholars)	>160 participants to co-creation Labs
		WP4, WP5	M9	M26	6.2	3 online sessions for the EU/transnational Lab	3 online sessions
		WP4, WP5	M9	M26	6.2	3 face to face meetings for the EU/transnational Lab	3 face to face meetings
		WP4, WP5	M9	M26	6.3	>240 participants joining the 3 online transnational Lab sessions,	>240 participants (online labs)

innovations, bridging with EU and national policies.	WP4, WP5	M9	M26	6.4	>90 participants joining (excluding consortium partners, min 3 x country + other EU level networks) the 3 face to face meetings	>90 participants (for 3 face-to-face meetings)
	WP4, WP5	M21	M31	6.5	>16 organizations/networks partnering locally to develop testing actions (FIERCE actions) in T4.4	>16 organizations/networks in FIERCE actions (T4.4)
	WP4, WP5	M10	M34	6.6	3 Policy Briefs (M15, M20, M27)	3 Policy Briefs
	WP4, WP5	M10	M34	6.6	1 Toolkit	1 Toolkit
	WP4, WP5	M19	M27	6.7	>500 participants of the online version of the Feminist Summer School	>500 online users (Feminist Summer School)

2.2. Milestones

The identified project milestones are presented in the table below. The complete and always up-to-date milestone table is provided within section “List of milestones” of the DoA.

#	Milestone title	Lead	Due	W P	Status ¹	Means of verification
1	Successful completion of the field work	UL	M16	1	In progress	Successful delivery of the field work
2	Analysis of media and parliamentary debates, and social network analysis completed	UL	M26	1	In progress	Successful delivery of media and SNA
3	Methodological framework established	SNS	M6	2	In progress	Successful delivery of the methodological framework
4	Mapping of actors, debates and policy outcomes completed	SNS	M6	2	In progress	Successful completion of the mapping and the outcomes of the research
5	Methodological framework established for multidimensional and multi-level crosscountry comparative analysis	AAU	M27	3	In progress	Successful delivery of the methodological framework
6	Cross country comparative analysis completed	SNS	M36	3	Not started	Successful delivery of the comparative analysis
7	First co-creation cycle completed with the FIERCE's Labs	SV	M10	4	Not started	Successful realisation of the FIERCE labs
8	Open call for partnership for FIERCE actions drafted and published	SV	M22	4	Not started	Successful organising of the FIERCE open call
9	Launch of the Transnational Feminist Network	EA	M25	5	Not started	Successful delivery of the transnational feminist network
10	Activists Summer School completed	EA	M27	5	Not started	Successful delivery of the activists summer schools
11	Launch of the Project Website	VIL	M2	6	Completed	Successful launching and handling of the project website
12	Successful organisation of the kick-off Meeting	VIL	M2	7	Completed	Successful organisation and completion of the kick-off meeting
13	Project Conclusion and final review	VIL	M36	7	Not started	Successful completion of the project

¹ Status as that was at the time this document report was formulated.

2.3. Work Package Structure

A detailed work package structure is presented in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement within section 3.1 “Work plan and resources” and more specifically under section 3.1.1 “Overall structure of the work plan” of the DoA. An overview of the FIERCE Work Plan Structure is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2 – FIERCE WP Structure

Table 2 - FIERCE List of Work Packages

#	Work Package Title	Lead Participant	PMs	Start	End
1	Anti-gender rhetorics/movements and their influence on democracies	UL	63	1	26
2	Feminist movements and democracies	SNS	60	1	26
3	Cross-cutting comparison of thematic areas within a policy framework and feminist contributions to engendering democracy	AAU	76	25	36
4	Participatory research co-creation Labs	SV	53	1	32
5	Innovative strategies and solution pathways	EA	57	10	36
6	Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation	VIL	34	1	36
7	Project management & Coordination	VIL	28	1	36

2.4. Deliverables

A detailed deliverable list is presented in the table below. The official and always up-to-date list is presented in Annex 1 of the GA within section “List of Deliverables” of the DoA.

Table 3 - FIERCE List of Deliverable Reports

#	Deliverable name	Lead	Due	Diss. Level	Type	WP	Description
D1.1	Report on detailed research and methodological guidelines for case studies and on the mapping of actors, debates, and policy outcomes	UL	M6	PU - Public	R - Document, Report	WP1	The report provides a comprehensive mapping of the main anti-feminist and anti-gender actors in each of the eight country cases, with focus on the period 2010-2021. It identifies the most salient gender-issues at stake and the way these cluster together according to main themes and in response to critical junctures.
D1.2	Report of field work results	AAU	M26	PU - Public	R - Document, Report	WP1	The report presents the results of the content and frame analysis of the media and parliamentary debates and of the interviews with the political party representatives. It also includes a social network analysis with information about the interconnections, communication and information sharing of the anti-feminist and anti-gender milieus on social media platforms
D2.1	Report on detailed research and methodological guidelines for case studies and on the mapping of actors, debates and policy outcomes	SNS	M6	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP2	The report will offer a first broad mapping of the cases and detailed methodological guidelines to secure that all partners are able to conduct an harmonised field work research.

D2.2	Report of field-work results	AAU	M26	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP2	The report will describe and analyse both the internal practices and tensions of the feminist movements and their discourses with regard to gender issues/debates within the five selected areas (definition of the problems, their demands and envisaged policy solutions, alliances, and their impact on institutional politics). It will also include Social Network Analysis of key feminist campaigns.
D3.1	Methodological framework and guidelines for comparative analysis	UCM	M27	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP3	The report outlines the analytical tools which integrate the methodological framework for the multi-dimensional and multi-level cross country analysis to be carried out in T3.2 and T3.3 as well as the guidelines indicating each step to be taken.
D3.2	Report on multidimensional and multilevel comparative analysis of key thematic areas	MI	M36	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP3	The report selects and analyses the most salient gender issues across the country cases and key thematic areas and discloses findings as regards policy impact and policy change with reference to contextual dimensions, levels and patterns of alliances, including dynamics of in/exclusion.
D3.3	Report on cross country analysis and on emerging democratic innovations	AAU	M36	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP3	The report evaluates feminist strategies of policy influence and intersectional framings, alliances and agenda-setting with the aim of assessing their potential for inclusive and democratic innovations.
D4.1	Co-creation methodology and dialogue sessions reports	SV	M12	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP4	This report will present the methodology to be followed by facilitators to organize and run the co-creation sessions. It will include a portfolio of co-creation techniques, adaptable to face to face and online settings. Two updated versions on M20 and M27, will allow to tailor the programme content wise to the ongoing results of WP 1 and 2 and will include reports of the dialogue sessions
D4.2	Report on democratic innovative practices	EA	M31	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP4	EA includes a presentation and an analysis of FIERCE piloted actions. It will rely on analytical dimensions devised with all partners and in alignment with WP1, 2 and 3.

D5.1	Feminist Activists online course	SV	M34	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP5	A curriculum for an online self-paced course will be created based on edited and subtitled videos from recordings of the Summer School, complemented with sets of assignments/exercises.
D5.2	Initial Policy briefs	EA	M15	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP5	Policy briefs will be prepared and released in alignment with the co-creation cycles, on M15 and two updated versions will be provided on M20 and M27.
D5.3	Final Policy briefs and Toolkit	EA	M34	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP5	The policy toolkit will be multimedia based, including written and printed text but also videos and infographics. It will be in English, with an executive summary in the languages of the project and include the policy briefs that will be released and disseminated in the course of the project.
D6.1	Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	VIL	M6	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP6	This report will include the overall strategy, goals, objectives, activities, targets, guidelines and materials for all the tasks of the WP.
D6.2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 1	VIL	M18	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP6	The overall progress of the WP will be reported with emphasis on the activities performed, lessons learnt and an updated planning for the final period
D6.3	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 2	VIL	M36	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP6	The overall progress of the WP will be reported, with emphasis on the activities performed, the policy recommendations and the benefits of the various stakeholders involved as well as it will include the replication/transferability guidebook of the project.
D7.1	Project Handbook & Management Plan	VIL	M3	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP7	This report will define all the project management framework, quality control procedures, detailed description of project structure, partner responsibilities, quality control mechanisms, documentation control and formats and exchange rules.
D7.2	Data management plan	VIL	M6	PU - Public	R — Document, report	WP7	The plan concerning the open research data management according to the guidelines for data and other outputs management in the Horizon Europe Annotated Grant Agreement and DMP Template. This deliverable will be updated at M18 and M36 with the ongoing progress.

D7.3	Ethics Documents for check	VIL	M5	SEN - Sensitive	R — Document, report	WP7	Prior to the Ethics check on WP8, this deliverable will include all documentation required for the ethics check (if needed e.g Ethics approvals, templates of informed consent, etc.)
D7.4	Project Progress report	VIL	M24	SEN - Sensitive	R — Document, report	WP7	In this report information of progress will be collected from all WPs and objectives and will be needed to monitor the progress of the project in between the first review of M15 and the last review of M36.
D8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	VIL	M3	SEN - Sensitive	ETHICS	WP8	1st report of the Ethics Advisor. Given the fact that the consortium did not mention any problems on the use of personal data (and the risk of stigmatisation etc...), it seems necessary to add an Ethics Advisor (who is trained in data protection) to the project, who can support in the definition/review of initial ethical protocols(M3) and with bringing a strong understanding of the ethical needs. The Advisor may be called to review the implementation of the plans/protocols after the 1st year of activity
D8.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	VIL	M1	SEN - Sensitive	ETHICS	WP8	Appointment of the Ethics Advisor. Given the fact that the consortium did not mention any problems on the use of personal data (and the risk of stigmatisation etc...), it seems necessary to add an Ethics Advisor (who is trained in data protection) to the project, who can support in the definition/review of initial ethical protocols(M3) and with bringing a strong understanding of the ethical needs. The Advisor may be called to review the implementation of the plans/protocols after the 1st year of activity
D8.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	VIL	M12	SEN - Sensitive	ETHICS	WP8	2nd report of the the Ethics Advisor. Given the fact that the consortium did not mention any problems on the use of personal data (and the risk of stigmatisation etc...), it seems necessary to add an Ethics Advisor (who is trained in data protection) to the project, who can support in the definition/review of initial ethical protocols(M3) and with bringing a strong understanding of the ethical

							needs. The Advisor may be called to review the implementation of the plans/protocols after the 1st year of activity
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3. Project Management Approach

3.1. Overall Management Strategy

The FIERCE project management description is found in the Description of the Action (DoA), Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement (GA), as part of the contract with the European Commission (EC), along with the project scope and baselines. The Consortium Agreement is based on the contract with the European Commission and is another legal instrument establishing the fundamental rights and obligations in the relationships between partners. All other parts of project management rely on these two. Quality and risk management permeate all activities of the project and act as safeguards. Quality is assured and risks are assessed for both project products and project management practices. All activities end with the communication of decisions, changes and actions to consortium members and the EC.

The core activities to ensure the project stays on track are the scope, cost and schedule management. They keep the project in line with what the Annex 1 of the GA prescribes that the project should do, cost and how long it should take to accomplish its objectives respectively. Procurement management describes how to handle purchases needed to execute the project at a partner level, while staff management defines the needs in terms of people, their roles and who is going to fill those roles in terms of their expertise. The core activities of project management lead to decisions and changes in both the work of the project and its management, but cannot impose practices or plans on the partners without their approval. Core activities are managed through change management, which feeds into communications management ensuring that information reaches all appropriate audiences. Quality management contributes to establishing the relevant to the project quality control and quality assurance activities for ensuring an efficient collaboration among the consortium partners and delivery of project results; whereas the risk management is necessary for providing the process and techniques for the evaluation and control of potential project risks, focusing on their precautionary diagnosis and handling.

3.2. Project Management Structure / Approach

The FIERCE consortium consists of 11 partners from 8 different countries (Greece, Denmark, Italy, Spain, France, Poland, Slovenia, Turkey) with multidisciplinary expertise in intersecting and complementary research areas. Geographically the partners cover all the main regions of Europe, ensuring that the project outcomes will be adaptable across the Union. The consortium includes **7 universities** (AAU, SNS, UCM, UG, AUTH, KU, UL), **2 NGOs** (EA, MI), and **2 SMEs** (VIL, SV).

Figure 3 - FIERCE Consortium Map

Table 4 - FIERCE Partners & Contact details

No	Participant organisation name	Country	Reference person
1	VILABS (VIL)	Greece	Mpampis Chatzimallis
2	Aalborg University (AAU)	Denmark	Susi Meret

3	Scuola Normale Superiore di Pisa (SNS)	Italy	Donatella Della Porta
4	Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM)	Spain	Inés Campillo
5	Smart Venice (SV)	Italy	Maria Sangiuliano
6	European Alternatives (EA)	France	Ségolène Pruvot
7	University of Gdansk (UG)	Poland	Grzegorz Piotrowski
8	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)	Greece	Alexandros Kioupkiolis
9	Mirovni Institute (MI)	Slovenia	Mojca Pajnik
10	Koç University (KU)	Turkey	Özlem Altan Olcay
11	University of Ljubljana (UL)	Slovenia	Roman Kuhar

Overall, project management encompasses operational, technical, financial and administrative coordination as well as the supervision of various activities within the project. To manage a project of the size and complexity of FIERCE, a professional and flexible management structure is vital. Transparent decision-making processes are required to both encourage project development and foster confidence amongst the project consortium. Conflict management should be focused on prevention and be apparent from project commencement. Contingency plans have to be derived. Clear and pragmatic decision-making and communication pathways and prompt reporting mechanisms are necessary. For this reason, each consortium partner will nominate a Management Representative (often referred to as partner project manager or primary contact). If necessary, one person can fulfil more than one role. Furthermore, the Project Coordinator (ViLabs) will be responsible for the coordination of the project and leading its QA activities, in the framework of WP7. The Project Coordinator is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority. The Project Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and this Consortium Agreement.

To tackle its coordination and technical goals, FIERCE is organized into 7 Work Packages (WPs). WPs are further divided into WP Tasks. Therefore, a Work Package Leader per WP and a Task Leader per Task are nominated, according to the project plan. WP leaders and Task leaders are responsible for coordinating efforts at the WP and Task level accordingly.

The FIERCE project management takes into account all the partners' interests and expertise, in order to ensure an effective project's time-plan and execution. The main objectives of the project management that have been defined are to:

- Ensure the effective administrative, financial and technical management of the project,
- Identify quantifiable and targeted measurement criteria of project progress and clear milestones,
- Ensure that the project results are achieved within the proposed resources (time, cost, resources),

- Apply quality assurance measures to all project-related procedures and products,
- Provide successful dissemination of the project's results and apply efficient exploitation activities and finally,
- Strengthen the co-operation of all project partners and external participants.

The figure below illustrates the management scheme that has been designed for the effective management and coordination of the FIERCE project.

Figure 4 - FIERCE Management Structure

The FIERCE hierarchical organization positioned above is comprised of the:

- **Project Plenary Board (PPB)**; the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium, which consists of one representative from each partner accountable for taking decisions for their organisations chaired by the Project Coordinator.
- **Project Coordinator (PC)**; Responsible for the day-to-day running of the project and for communication with the EC and the Project Officer.
- **Project Management team (PMT)**; the supervisory body for the execution of the Project which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly. It consists of the Coordinator and the Work package leaders. It runs the day-to-day and feeds the PPB with proposed solutions.
- **Work Package (WP) Leaders**; partners responsible for Work Package related decision-making and for the preparation of input for the PMT and the Project Coordinator.

The basic philosophy of this structure is that, although the PPB has the ultimate responsibility for the output and outcome of the project, the day-to-day management is delegated to the PMT.

In this structure, the key project management persons have specific functions:

- The Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for the day-to-day management of the project. The PC will chair the PMT meetings, will coordinate the work of work package leaders and strategic partners.
- The Scientific Coordinators (SC) are responsible for the scientific vision of the project and for overseeing the implementation of the project, guaranteeing the work is meeting the scientific objectives proposed.

Each Work Package/Task is led by the partner most competent in the domain concerned, as identified within the Annex 1 of the GA. Work Package leaders and Task leaders are responsible for coordinating efforts in the Work-Package and Task level accordingly. Reporting on the successful completion of tasks, progress on deliverables, and on problems, delays and conflicts and proposals for decision-making, starts from the partners involved at the Task level and escalates up to the final decision body that is the **Project Plenary Board**. Active support will be given and formal controls will be applied to ensure sufficient feedback loops and close, effective, and efficient inter-relation and co-operation of all parties involved, through quality and risk management.

However, the **Project Coordinator** retains the responsibility to intervene at any point of the management structure, if the cohesion of the project is threatened. More specifically, in the case of:

- Decisions which have broader project implications and/or involve communication with the Project Officer and contradict the DoA,
- Delays, costs overruns or other lack of project progress against the objectives described in the DoA,
- Conflicts, which the Work Package leader is unable to resolve or whose resolution remains elusive for an extended period of time, threatening the overall project progress.

The various project management bodies and roles are further described in the FIERCE Consortium Agreement.

3.3. Roles and entities

Successful collaboration and continuous communication among partners of the project and the parties identified as part of the stakeholders' ecosystem, are the keys to achieving the project goals. For this reason, specific roles and management entities have been identified:

Project Coordinator (PC) (Mpampis Chatzimallis, ViLabs)

In line with the FIERCE Consortium Agreement (Article 6.4), the role of the PC is to represent the project and the consortium, report to the Commission, monitor overall project performance, administer project resources and promote project visibility. The PC will chair the Project Plenary Board and Project Management Team meetings and is responsible for the project formal communication with the Commission and other stakeholders. Mpampis Chatzimallis (ViLabs) brings considerable experience in the dual fields of democracy and gender studies and as such has experience managing multipartner research projects. He has experience in the coordination of complex EC-funded projects and has already successfully coordinated large EU projects, while he has worked as deputy coordinator for many others.

Scientific coordinators (SC) (Prof. Susi Meret and Lise Rolandsen Agustin, AAU)

The role of the Scientific coordinators is to lead project task 7.2 Scientific Coordination and management and in detail: a) Ensure the targeted implementation of overall project goals; b) Continuously compare

actual and planned implementation of WP objectives (in relation to quality, quantity, time and cost); c) High-level synchronization of goals and ambitions of individual partners; d) Coordination of Knowledge-exchange with the Advisory Board. Both Professors have experience in managing multi-partner research projects.

Quality and Risk Manager (QRM) (Kyriaki Karydou, VILABS)

The Quality and Risk Manager is responsible for enforcing monitoring and assessment of the project's quality. The QRM reports to the PC (Project coordinator). Kyriaki Karydou has several years' experience in management and coordination roles within large EC-funded projects.

Work Package Leaders (WPL)

Each WP has an assigned leader who will be in charge of coordinating activities of their WP, execute fine-grained plans and allow monitoring of the activities of the WP. WPL's report to the PC, QRM, or SC depending on the nature of the issues. WPLs are further supported by Task Leaders.

Table 5 - FIERCE Work Package Leaders

WP nr.	Partner	Main Responsible	Deputy
WP1	UL	Roman Kuhar	Rok Smrdelj
WP2	SNS	Donatella Della Porta	Giada Bonu
WP3	AAU	Susi Meret	Lise Rolandsen Agustin
WP4	SV	Maria Sangiuliano	Oriana Salomon Balsamo
WP5	EA	Ségolène Pruvot	Niccolo Milanese
WP6	ViLabs	Kyriaki Karydou	Anna Papadimitropoulou
WP7	ViLabs	Mpampis Chatzimallis	Kyriaki Karydou
WP8	ViLabs	Mpampis Chatzimallis	Kyriaki Karydou

The Project Plenary Board (PPB)

The **Project Plenary Board (PPB)** shall consist of the Project Coordinator (Chair) and one representative of each Party (hereinafter referred to as "Member").

Each Member shall be deemed to be duly authorised to deliberate, negotiate and decide on all matters listed in Section **Error! Reference source not found.** of this Consortium Agreement.

The Project Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Project Plenary Board, unless decided otherwise by the Project Plenary Board.

The Project Management Team (PMT)

The Project Management Team shall consist of the **Project Coordinator (Chair of PMT)** and the **Work Package Leaders (WPL)** (some of which may hold additional roles such as Quality Manager, Dissemination Manager and Scientific Coordination of the project).

The PMT shall support the PC on the following:

(i) Ensure the targeted implementation of overall project goals and risk evaluation, (ii) Continuously compare actual and planned implementation of WP objectives (in relation to quality, quantity and time), (iii) maintaining contractual documents, (iv) organizing project launch and follow-up (e.g., periodic project boards meetings, progress review, conflict resolution), (v) coordinating timely production of deliverables and reports, (vi) providing assistance to partners on administrative issues.

Table 6 - Project Management Team

Project Management Team
WP7/WP8 Leader - Project Coordinator (Mpampis Chatzimallis)
Scientific Coordinators (Susi Meret and Lise Rolandsen Agustin)
Quality and Risk Manager (Kyriaki Karydou)
WP1 Leader (Roman Kuhar)
WP2 Leader (Donatella Della Porta)
WP3 Leader (Susi Meret)
WP4 Leader (Maria Sangiuliano)
WP5 Leader (Ségolène Pruvot)
WP6 Leader (Kyriaki Karydou)

External Advisory Board

An Advisory Board (AB) is appointed and steered by the Project Plenary Board (PPB). The AB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the Project Plenary Board. The Expert Advisory Board provides non-binding advice and support to the project activities.

The **Advisory Board** also supports the FIERCE project during its implementation. It provides non-binding advice and support to the project activities. Its informal nature aims to ensure inclusiveness and respect for the different views which might arise regarding the evolution of the project. A representative of the Advisory Board is allowed to participate in the physical or online meetings of the Project Management Team. The Advisory Board is Coordinated by ViLabs (Project Coordinator). The Consortium may decide to invite further members taking into account the recommendations of EC or Advisory Board recommendations. The advisory board consists of the following members, listed below:

Prof. Birgit Sauer

- Professor of Political Science at the University of Vienna.
- *Expert in:* Gender and Governance, Gender Politics, Theories of the State and Institutions, Politics and Emotions, Right-wing Populism and gender.

Dr. Victoria Showunmi

- Associate Professor in Education at UCL Institute of Education, UK.
- *Expert in:* Collaborative Social Science, Cultural Understanding, Human Wellbeing, Justice & Equality.

Prof. Birte Siim

- Professor Emerita in Political Science at the Aalborg University in Denmark.
- *Expert in:* Democracy, Citizenship, Intersectional Gender, Migration and Transnationalism.

Independent Ethical advisor

According to the guidelines² provided by the EC, the Ethics Advisor will assess the procedure throughout the lifecycle of the project, support the definition/review of initial ethical protocols (M3) and reassure the proper management of project data and the overall compliance with GDPR. The Advisor will be called to review the implementation of the plans/protocols after the 1st year of activity. The Advisor will support the coordinating organisation to secure that all project activities are in full line with articles 13, 14, 15 and 16 of the FIERCE Grant Agreement.

² (2022). Roles and Functions of Ethics Advisors/Ethics Advisory Boards in EC-funded Projects, 05 July 2021 Retrieved 09 November 2022, from https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/roles-and-functions-of-ethics-advisory-ethics-advisory-boards-in-ec-funded-projects_he_en.pdf

4. Project Baselines

4.1. Introduction

The project's baseline is used to measure how performance deviates from the plan, and it is defined as the original scope, cost and schedule and must be completely documented before the project execution and control activities are initiated. Of course, the project performance measurement would only be meaningful if an accurate baseline is set. Once the project is initiated, the project's baseline is put under change control to enable the evaluation of any further change and/or impact on the project. In the event where there is an approved change to the project baseline, the new baseline is redefined as the original plan plus the approved changes. The project scope is defined in section 2.1 of this document, while a reference to the project original cost and schedule is made within this chapter.

In addition, a section is dedicated to the quality baseline that records the minimum project indicators, which are an important performance management tool for the project to help measure progress in achieving the associated goals and meeting the basic requirements

4.1. Schedule Baseline

The Overall Gantt chart in section 3.1.2 "Gantt Chart" within Part B of the Description of Action (DoA), presents the schedule baseline of the project. It can be found below, but in case of conflicting versions, the version in the DoA is the prevailing one.

		2023												2024												2025												
		Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	
FIERCE		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36	
WP1	Anti-gender rhetorics/movements and their influence on democracies																																					
T1.1	Setting up the research framework and mapping actors, debates and policy outcomes						D1.1																															
T1.2	Discourses and communication strategies from anti-gender movements																																					
T1.3	Anti gender movements impact on institutional representation and their relations with political parties																																					
WP2	Feminist movements and democracies																																					
T2.1	Setting up the research framework and mapping actors, debates and policy outcomes						D2.1																															
T2.2	Discourses, communication strategies and internal practices and debates within feminist movements																																					
T2.3	Feminist movement relations with other political actors and impact on the institutional arena																																					
WP3	Cross-cutting comparison of thematic areas within a policy framework and feminist contributions to engendering democracy																																					
T3.1	Setting up the framework for the cross-country comparative analysis																																					
T3.2	A multidimensional and multi-level cross-country comparative analysis of key thematic areas																																					D3.2
T3.3	Cross-country comparative analysis of feminist innovations to rekindle democratic processes																																					D3.3
WP4	Participatory research co-creation Labs																																					
T4.1	Research-practice co-creation methodology and FIERCE's Labs set up																																					
T4.2	Coordinating/facilitating co-creation sessions																																					
T4.3	Reporting on results																																					
T4.4	FIERCE actions: Testing democratic innovation actions in partnership with local and national feminist movements																																					D4.2
WP5	Innovative strategies and solution pathways																																					
T5.1	Establishment of a "transnational network" bringing together feminist movements and public actors																																					D5.1
T5.2	Feminist Activists Summer School																																					
T5.3	Policy briefs and toolkit																																					D5.3
WP6	Dissemination, Communication, Sustainability & Exploitation																																					
T6.1	Communication and Dissemination							D6.1																														
T6.2	Exploitation and sustainability																																					
T6.3	Building and engaging a community of stakeholders																																					
T6.4	Synergies with related clusters, projects and initiatives																																					D6.3
WP7	Project management & Coordination																																					
T7.1	Project coordination and management							D7.1																														
T7.2	Scientific coordination and management																																					
T7.3	Operational, quality/risk control and ethical issues																																					
T7.4	Open Research Data Management																																					
WP8	Ethics requirements																																					

4.2. Resource Calendar

The resource calendar indicates the overall envisaged effort resource consumption spend by all Work packages in person-months per month for the whole project duration. This is derived by cumulating the individual planned effort resource spent by each partner at the beginning of the project according to the efforts declared within the .xlsx file that is used internally for project scheduling". Each WP leader is responsible for submitting to the PC at the beginning of the project their planned efforts for the whole project duration in relation to the Tasks where assigned person months are allocated, and the PC is responsible for maintaining a consolidated version of it for the whole project.

4.3. Cost Baseline

The cost baseline concerns the amount of resources that the project is predicted to cost and when those resources will be used throughout the project lifespan. This is derived according to the:

- **Project Budget** (as declared in table of Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement: "Estimated budget for the action")
- **Effort Allocation** (as declared in table of section: "Staff Effort" in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement)
- **Project Work Plan** (described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement)

In essence, the cost baseline converts efforts to personnel cost per month, including indirect, other costs and subcontracting expenses. For the calculation of the project cost baseline the same policy as with the definition of the resource calendar described above is applied. In this instance, all consortium partners at the beginning of the project will need to provide the PC with their planned expenses per reporting period, and their average person rate in case this is different from what it is documented in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. Every 6 months and also by the end of each reporting period (M7, M13, M20, M25, M32, M36), all partners will be requested to provide the PC with the actual costs consumed.

4.4. Quality Baseline - KPIs

Project indicators are an important performance management tool for projects to help measure progress in achieving their goals and meeting requirements, hence, it is important that the chosen success criteria are quantifiable and critical to the success of the project. This section provides performance indicators for meeting the specific objectives of the project in the points below. These points will be reviewed, updated and refined during the course of the project through the scope and change management processes, to ensure that all partners have the opportunity to contribute to the discussion and help select the appropriate performance indicators for the project. The project will be measured against its performance indicators at a number of stages:

- the two project reviews; and
- within additional internal quality reviews

The results of performance measurement and evaluation (indicators and their values) will be part of the progress reporting to the European Commission.

The baseline Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that have been identified for the purposes of the FIERCE project are detailed in Part B of the DoA and more specifically in the following sections:

- Section 1.1.2 “Objectives and ambition”
- Section 2.1.2 “Project’s Expected Impacts specified in this destination”
- Section 2.2.1 “Dissemination Strategy and Measures”
- Section 2.2.2 “Communication Strategy and Measures”
- Section 2.2.3 “Exploitation Strategy and Measures”

5. Quality Assurance and Management

Integral part of the project management plan is the quality assurance procedures should provide the solid ground for successful, timely and quality implementation of the project activities. The quality management procedures defined in this deliverable form a common standard to be applied and followed throughout the entire project lifetime. Therefore, the main purpose of this report is to define a consistent set of procedures, processes and guidelines in order to ensure high quality standards of the project outcomes. The quality assurance procedures defined in this document focus on:

- **Performance management:** Assessing the progress of the work on a regular basis
- **Communication Management:** Managing the interaction between partners during the work execution
- **Documents / deliverables management:** Defining how and when the documentation and the deliverables have to be exchanged by the partners and submitted to the European Commission

5.1. Quality management roles

All consortium partners have mutual and equal responsibility to produce high quality deliverables and project outcomes.

The **Risk and Quality manager**, member of the Project Management Team is responsible for ensuring the project's quality aspect, applying the following duties:

- Maintain the quality assurance procedures with the support of a representative from each partner.
- Act as a focal point for quality issues and liaise with partners to ensure that an appropriate level of quality is maintained for each element of the project.
- Ensure that activities and reports are completed to an adequate quality and in a timely manner.
- Monitor and audit the project activities for conformance with the project plans, in particular performing milestone reviews of contractual deliverables.
- Initiate action to prevent the occurrence of any non-conformity.

All **WP Leaders** should assist the Risk and Quality manager and shall therefore ensure:

- To adhere to the quality assurance procedures adequately, and
- To immediately inform the Risk and Quality manager of any problems related to quality assurance.

The Risk and Quality manager should be assisted also by the **Scientific Coordinators** to ensure the scientific quality and propose improvements when necessary

5.2. Performance management

Performance management is about the management of partner's performance in relation to the project milestones and objectives. The key tool to monitor the project progress and how performance is deviating from the plan, is the project Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These are defined already within the Grand Agreement. However, during the project progress these Indicators are continuously evaluated and updated according to the real project implementation circumstances, cost and schedule.

The project indicators will be continuously monitored throughout the project progress and will be evaluated on a frequent basis: (i) every six months within the internal and official project reporting, among the consortium (ii) the results of performance measurement and evaluation (indicators and their values) will be part of the progress reporting to the European Commission, therefore every 18 months during the technical review, any adaptations will be discussed between the consortium and the European Commission. The project Coordinator is in charge to preparing the reports and ask each partner for any additional contributions.

In addition, the Coordinator organizes **bi-weekly online meetings** in which the Work Package briefly report the progress to ensure the early identification of deviations from the planned project targets including delays or early finishes and their implications on the overall progress.

The indicator targets set by FIERCE in the Grand Agreement define its level of ambition, help to monitor progress throughout implementation and allow saying at the end of the project whether the objectives have been achieved.

All indicators under FIERCE are expressed in quantity (such as ‘the number of’, ‘percentage of’) in order to be able to measure results and outputs objectively, but they need to be completed by qualitative aspects (such as addressed target groups, in which place the change is produced).

To set a good indicator system at a project level, the indicators should also be smart, which means:

- **Specific:** is it clear what exactly will be measured, in what geographical area measurements will be made, what units etc.
- **Measurable:** will the project be able to collect accurate information to measure progress towards the targets set? The information required for measurements should be quite easy to collect. It should be aware that different regions and countries collect data in different ways, thus all partners should be able to monitor and report on the indicators selected.
- **Achievable:** closely linked to identifying what changes are anticipated as a result of the project work and whether the results planned are realistic.
- **Relevant:** will the indicators measure all of the project’s key activities?
- **Timed:** stating when something should happen (e.g. increase in visitor numbers by the end of the project).

5.3. Quality Standards that apply to deliverables and procedures

During the FIERCE project implementation, a number of project outcomes will be made. All these deliveries should adhere to certain quality standards. Each of these deliveries should be validated and verified before delivering to the EC. Without standards and procedures, the risk is that team members will complete their work with different understandings of the procedures they are required to follow and the results they are intended to produce, resulting in productivity losses, quality losses and schedule delays.

The development of standards and procedures is an iterative process. Thus, the standards and procedures are never complete but can expect to evolve and be enhanced as the project proceeds. As the procedures are put in place and implemented, during the project progress improvements will be identified and introduced under the control of the Quality Manager.

The project deliveries can be generally categorized as documents and reports (Public Deliverables, Progress reports, Policy Briefings, Scientific publications), events (final conference, trainings), and online events. All project deliveries will be published centrally by the project website. It has been set up in order to attract large number of target groups and the broad general public. They will be able to find regularly updated information about the project, its progress, contact information, project achievements and results.

5.3.1. Quality of events offline/online

All events planned within the project need to be professionally organized. The host organisation will be responsible for providing the smooth realization of the event, which includes all necessary arrangements and coordination, preparation of invitation packages (invitation letters, agendas, etc), details on location /online tool, available accommodation and travel arrangements, etc.

The deadline for completing necessary preparation activities depends on the event itself, but it must provide enough time for participants' registration and travel preparations.

Additionally, the host organisation will be responsible for provision of all materials required for the event (promotional or informative material, supporting documents, printed agendas, etc), as well as for the elaboration of reports/minutes on the held event upon its completion.

Every planned event within the FIERCE project must also meet the requirements regarding the structure and the number of target audience.

All the material used for the organisation and implementation of such events should have the FIERCE project brand. All templates with the project logo have been prepared and are available on the Project Repository.

5.4. FIERCE Deliverable Reports

FIERCE will mainly use the peer-review method for determining quality. Through this method, the deliverables are assessed for completeness and fitness for purpose. A quality inspection is a systematic, structured assessment of a deliverable conducted in a documented and organised fashion. This approach to quality inspection can be used both during the development of deliverables and to mark the completion and approval of deliverables.

5.5. Deliverable Preparation Guidelines

A total of 22 deliverables will need to be submitted to the European Commission in the course of FIERCE project. To ensure smooth and timely delivery of deliverable as well as homogeneous presentation, a set of guidelines for the preparation of deliverables is presented here.

5.5.1. Deliverable Types and Confidentiality Levels

The deliverables are classified according to the following types:

R: Document, Report

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

Insofar the confidentiality of deliverables and other documents, including presentations, is concerned, the following two (2) levels of security are considered:

PU: Public Usage. No restrictions on access (in secured PDF format).

SEN: Sensitive, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).

5.5.2. Deliverable Preparation and Peer Review Process

All deliverables should be formed according to the Deliverable template maintained within the Project repository (Microsoft Team). The template provides a deliverable identity sheet and specifies formatting for the most used elements of deliverable report. The partners responsible for the deliverable are required to ensure that before releasing the first deliverable draft to partners, it is in the correct template, specified format and the identity sheet is complete. The table below shows the process to be observed for preparing deliverables.

Figure 6 - Sample pages from Deliverable template

5.5.2.1. Deliverable Reviewers List

The following table lists the **internal Review Team** assigned per Deliverable. The goal is for each Deliverable to have two reviewers, in order to combine different perspectives in the review.

#	Deliverable	Lead	Reviewer 1	Reviewer 2	Due
D1.1	Report on detailed research and methodological guidelines for case studies and on the mapping of actors, debates, and policy outcomes	UL	SNS	AAU/ViLabs	M6

D1.2	Report of field work results	AAU	UL	SNS/ViLabs	M26
D2.1	Report on detailed research and methodological guidelines for case studies and on the mapping of actors, debates and policy outcomes	SNS	UL	AAU/ViLabs	M6
D2.2	Report of field-work results	AAU	SNS	UL/ViLabs	M26
D3.1	Methodological framework and guidelines for comparative analysis	UCM	AAU	AAU/ViLabs	M27
D3.2	Report on multidimensional and multilevel comparative analysis of key thematic areas	MI	AAU	UL/SNS	M36
D3.3	Report on cross country analysis and on emerging democratic innovations	AAU	SNS	UCM/UL	M36
D4.1	Co-creation methodology and dialogue sessions reports	SV	EA	AAU/ViLabs	M12
D4.2	Report on democratic innovative practices	EA	SV	AAU/ViLabs	M31
D5.1	Feminist Activists online course	SV	EA	AAU/ViLabs	M34
D5.2	Initial Policy briefs	EA	SV	AAU/ViLabs	M15
D5.3	Final Policy briefs and Toolkit	EA	SV	AAU/ViLabs	M34
D6.1	Overall Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	VIL	AAU	All partners	M6
D6.2	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 1	VIL	AAU	All partners	M18
D6.3	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation progress report 2	VIL	AAU	All partners	M36
D7.1	Project Handbook & Management Plan	VIL	AAU	All partners	M3
D7.2	Data management plan	VIL	AAU	All partners	M6
D7.3	Ethics Documents for check	VIL	AAU	All partners	M5
D7.4	Project Progress report	VIL	AAU	All partners	M24
D8.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	VIL	AAU	All partners	M3
D8.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	VIL	AAU	All partners	M1
D8.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	VIL	AAU	All partners	M12

It has been decided that the final version of submitted deliverables to the EC will be made available in PDF and word formats in a designated folder in Teams FIERCE Repository Folder named **Final Deliverables**.

5.5.3. Document Formats

The following software formats and version of production tools shall be used in the project:

Table 7 - Digital file formats

Data Type	File Format	Production Tool	Version
Word processing	.docx	Microsoft Word	“Word 2013” or newer, Google Docs
Tabular spread sheet information and graphs	.xlsx	Microsoft Excel	“Excel 2013” or newer, Google Docs
Presentations	.pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint	“PowerPoint 2013” or newer, Google Docs
Project Planning	.xlsx	Microsoft Excel	“Excel 2013” or newer, Google Docs
Images	.jpeg	Any software tools that can produce .jpeg files	
Portable Document Format	.pdf	Any software that can produce .pdf files	
Compressed files	.zip or .7z	Any software that can produce .zip or .7z files	

Documents for electronic distribution must be storable / retrievable in a Microsoft Windows 7 or higher environment supporting long names.

If the partner responsible for the delivery of any document using one of these format is using a higher version than the one mentioned, then the original version should also be included (preferably through a .zip format).

It is recommended that changes to draft Word documents are made with track changes on, unless the document author requests otherwise.

The partner shall ensure that the images are suitable for printing and, especially for those images to be used for dissemination purposes, that they can be embedded in larger printing.

The use of the PDF format is limited to its capability of obtaining files that are printable with the same layout regardless of the printer. This explicitly excludes the use of any modification capability that can be offered by a PDF capable tool.

5.5.4. Filename Conventions

The partners are expected to exchange several documents between them during the course of project work. In order to facilitate document identification and differentiation between multiple versions of the same document, the following file naming convention should be used for the final version of the documents uploaded in Microsoft Teams.

FIERCE _<document name>_<version>_<date>.extension

<date> : yyyy-mm-dd, e.g. 2022-07-15

<document name> short (3-4 words) document name, e.g. D7.1 Project Management Handbook

<version>: increasing number with decimals between public releases

When a partner makes comments or changes to a file, he/she should append his/her “_<company/person>” field just before the .extension.

These filename conventions apply to other electronic objects, besides documents, that are used to exchange project information, e.g. prototype code. If such an object is composed of multiple files organized within a directory structure (e.g. source code that has not been zipped into one file), the filename convention requirement applies only to the top directory name

6. Change Management Plan

6.1. Introduction

The Change Management Plan sets expectations on how the approach to changes will be managed, what defines a change, the purpose and role of the Project Plenary Board, and the overall change management process. All consortium members are expected to submit or request changes to the FIERCE project in accordance with this Change Management Plan and all requests and submissions will follow the process detailed herein.

6.2. Change Management Approach

The Change Management approach is not to be confused with the Change Control Process, which is detailed in Section 6.5. The approach provides the general principles to which the process must adhere. The Change Management approach introduces the following rules:

- Ensure changes are within scope and beneficial to the project
- Ensure that all proposed changes are described adequately, reviewed, and agreed upon, so they can be properly implemented and communicated to all consortium members
- Determine adequately how the change will be implemented
- Manage the change and its impacts as it is implemented

The Change Management process has been designed to make sure this approach is followed for all changes. By using this approach methodology, the FIERCE project will prevent unnecessary changes from occurring and focus its resources only on beneficial changes within the project scope.

6.3. Definition of Change

There are several types of change that may be requested and considered for the FIERCE project. Depending on the extent and type of proposed changes, changes to the project documentation (i.e. project contract, internal or external deliverables, reports and other documentation) may be required. Additionally, the communication of these changes may need to include any approved changes into projects plan and ensure all consortium partners are notified. Types of changes include:

Scheduling Changes: changes that will impact the approved project schedule, i.e. schedule baseline. These changes may require fast tracking or re-baselining the schedule depending on the significance of the impact.

Budget Changes: changes that will impact the approved project budget. These changes may require reallocation of budget or may require changes to the cost baseline and a contract amendment. Under any circumstances, no additional overall project funding will be approved.

Effort Changes: changes that will impact the effort allocated to specific tasks. Depending on the size of these changes, they may require contract amendment. For minor changes to the planned effort allocation partners with the involvement of WP leaders can address these issues between them while keeping the PC informed.

Scope Changes: changes that are necessary and impact the project scope which may be the result of unforeseen requirements. These changes will be reported and documented in project reports.

Quality Changes: changes that will impact the quality of project deliverables. Depending on the extent of the impact on quality, these changes may require the modification of impact indicators and the contract with the European Commission. These changes may be reported and documented in project deliverables and reports.

All changes must be communicated to the PC and management team and examined for their impact to scope, budget/effort, schedule and quality.

The **Project Coordinator (PC)** must ensure that any approved changes are communicated to the consortium partners. Additionally, as changes are approved, the Project Coordinator must ensure that the changes are captured in the project documentation where necessary and is ultimately responsible for their changes. These document updates must then be communicated to the consortium partners as well.

6.4. Change Process

The Project Plenary Board is the approval body for all change requests pertaining to FIERCE. For major changes affecting the contract and/or have overreaching impact on the project, the PPB will put the changes for approval to the European Commission and/or consortium. The PPB reviews all change requests, determines their impacts on the project risk, scope, cost, and schedule, and filters change requests.

As Change Requests (CR) are submitted to the TLs, WPLs by the project team members, they rate them and forward to the PC. The PC logs the requests in the change log. All change requests will be reviewed during the PPB meetings. For a change request to be approved, all PPB members must vote in favour. For changes impacting the contract, the PPB will consult the European Commission and proceed accordingly. In the event more information is needed for a particular change request, the request will be deferred and sent back to the requestor for more information or clarification. If a change is deemed critical, an ad hoc PPB meeting can be called in order to review the change prior to the next scheduled PPB meeting.

6.5. Change Control Process

The PC has overall responsibility for executing the change management process for each change request. The Change Control Process for the FIERCE Project will follow the steps below.

Table 8 - Change Control Process

#	Steps	Who	To Whom	When	CR Status
1	Identify the need for a change – Change requester will submit a change request via e-mail up the project hierarchy. The e-mail should contain at minimum the following information:	Project partner	WPL, TL	Immediately	Initiated

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the cause • Description of the change • Description of the suggested solution • Impacts to schedule, budget, effort, scope, risk and quality 				
2	<p>Conduct a first analysis on the impact of the change to risk, cost, schedule, quality, risk and scope and seek clarification from team members and the change requestor.</p> <p>They will determine its priority (i.e. Emergency or Standard) and impact (i.e. Critical, Significant, Standard) and forward to the PC along with a decision to discuss the request or not.</p>	WPL, TL	PC	Immediately	Initiated
3	<p>Logs the change request and decides to forward to the PPB immediately or wait until next PPB meeting.</p>	PC	PPB	Immediately	Logged
4	<p>The PPB members will conduct a full analysis on the impact of the change to risk, cost, schedule, quality, risk and scope and seek clarification from project partners and the change requestor.</p>	PPB	PPB	As needed	Evaluation
5	<p>The PPB will discuss the proposed change at the next PPB meeting. It will decide whether or not to approve each change request based on the available information or put the issue for discussion with the Consortium. For changes that require modification of the DoA, the Consortium agreement will be required.</p>	PPB	-	During PPB Meeting	Approved/ Rejected
6	<p>If a change is approved by the PPB, the PC will update the project documentation as necessary. S/he will inform all involved parties and monitor the implementation of the change.</p>	PC	PPB	As needed	Implementation

6.6. Change Request Evaluation Criteria

Change requests are evaluated using the following priority and impact criteria.

Table 9 - Change Request Priority Criteria

Priority	Description
Emergency	The change request is time critical and an accelerated authorization and planning is required.
Standard/Low	The change request can wait until the next scheduled project management meeting.

Table 10 - Change Request Impact Criteria

Impact	Description
Critical	Presents an extraordinary high risk which will impact the delivery of the project and/or may require a contract amendment.
Significant	It requires management decision at the level of the PC or TC and may have broader impact for the project.
Standard / Low	It is presented to the management for informational reasons only. The matter is routine and can be resolved at the WP level.

7. Communication and collaboration procedures

It is very important for the success of the project to ensure good communication among project partners and third-party entities. For the proper operation, the project should set up a fast, reliable, and easily accessible collaboration and communications infrastructure. FIERCE establishes communication through the intensive use of electronic communication tools (e.g., email, web-based project management tool, file sharing, video- conference, etc.). The project [website](#) is also used to enable fast and efficient exchanges of information.

7.1. Internal communication

In order to assure an efficient internal communication between partners, the FIERCE project adopts the following tools:

Physical meetings

All project partners are represented at physical consortium meetings. These meetings are chaired by the Project Coordinator. Consortium meetings are held to ensure all partners are informed of the overall progress against objectives and to ensure all partners are aware of the priorities for the next phase of development of the project. ViLabs is responsible for ensuring that consortium meetings take place at regular intervals over the duration of the project. Any concerns or suggestions put forward at Consortium meetings will be addressed in detail by the PMT. The Consortium meeting is primarily a communication mechanism to ensure all partners are aware of project progress and future priorities.

The project Coordinator is responsible to organize the consortium meetings, sending an invitation and agenda to all partners and preparing and circulating the minutes to partners within 7 calendar days after the meeting. The minutes can be amended by all members participating the meeting within 3-4 days after sending the first version. The Coordinator integrates all changes and releases the final version of the minutes notifying all partners accordingly.

The proposed time plan and locations of the physical meetings, as those have been identified during the formulation of the current deliverable report, are the following:

Table 11 - Physical meetings schedule

Type	Time	Place	Beneficiary
Project Meeting	M1-Sept 2022	Greece	VIL
Project Meeting	M7-March 2023	Denmark	AAU
Project Meeting	M12 – Aug 2023	Spain	UCM
Interim Review	M18 – Feb 2024	Belgium/Online	All
Project Meeting	M24- Aug 2024	France	EA

Project Meeting	M30- Feb 2025	Italy	SNS/SV
Project Conference	M36- Aug 2025	Belgium	ViLabs
Final Review	M38 – Oct 2025	Belgium/Online	All

In order to assure an efficient internal communication between partners, the FIERCE project adopts many online tools, including the E-mail and Mailing lists, Online meeting Tools and the Project Management Tool (Microsoft Teams).

E-Mail and Mailing lists

Mailing lists represent the major communication tools used in the FIERCE Project. All mailing lists are closed lists: only members registered for a particular list may send messages to the list and receive as well. To avoid unnecessary emails, each person posting to any of the email lists should ensure that the content of the message is appropriate for the recipients of the list selected. Any member may unsubscribe from any mailing list, any time.

FIERCE has already set-up and maintains the following mailing lists³:

- Project mailing list with **all** partners.
- Project mailing list with **financial staff**.
- Project Advisory Board mailing list with **the Advisory Board members, the PC and the SC**.

Online meeting Tool

[Microsoft Teams](#) is used to organize short remote meetings between partners. Remote meetings are held every two weeks. Additional online meetings can be arranged depending on the particular needs of the project. The information related to connecting to the meeting as well as the agenda is circulated no later than a couple of days before the meeting. The online meetings are also recorded, with the agreement of all participants. The minutes are prepared in the format of the Word Document and uploaded to the Project Repository (Microsoft Teams), within 72 hours after the online meeting.

Project Management Tool

FIERCE is using Microsoft Teams also for the project management at internal level. It is managed by the Coordinator (VIL) and offers a Collaborative Working Environment equipped by useful tools and functionalities to support collaboration within the consortium in all phases of the project. The platform allows project progress monitoring, by being constantly informed about the users' activities.

All partners involved in the project have access to the platform. The access to the platform is controlled by a username and password connected to the personal user's account). All project participants are granted access to the shared workspace. Each project partner is responsible to notify the PC/ViLabs of changes in project participants in their organization, in order to allow ViLabs to update the lists of users involved in the various work packages. Any member may also delete the account at any time.

³ The actual email addresses are not included as a measure to avoid security threats.

Currently, the main sections that FIERCE has set up are:

Task Boards: FIERCE organised a Board for each WP to see the flow of activities (cards) and get a fuller representation of the planned activities. Every card includes a description of the planned activity, the assigned persons, the deadline, and the progress.

Figure 7- Screenshot of Task Boards within the Project Management Tool

Milestones: FIERCE includes all project milestones, along with the Deliverables. Each record includes the description of the milestone, the involved participants, its deadline and the progress. The milestones are depicted as:

- Upcoming, shows all upcoming milestones, including milestones due today, on that project.
- Late, shows all late/overdue milestones on that project.
- Completed, shows all the completed milestones on that project.

#	Milestone title	Lead	Due date	WP	Status	Means of verification
1	Successful completion of the field work	UL	M16	1	In progress	Successful delivery of the field work
2	Analysis of media and parliamentary debates, and social network analysis completed	UL	M26	1	In progress	Successful delivery of media and SNA
3	Methodological framework established	SNS	M6	2	In progress	Successful delivery of the methodological framework
4	Mapping of actors, debates and policy outcomes completed	SNS	M6	2	In progress	Successful completion of the mapping and the outcomes of the research
5	Methodological framework established for multidimensional and multi-level crosscountry comparative analysis	AAU	M27	3	In progress	Successful delivery of the methodological framework
6	Cross country comparative analysis completed	SNS	M36	3	Not started	Successful delivery of the comparative analysis
7	First co-creation cycle completed with the FIERCE's Labs	SV	M10	4	Not started	Successful realisation of the FIERCE labs
8	Open call for partnership for FIERCE actions drafted and published	SV	M22	4	Not started	Successful organising of the FIERCE open call
9	Launch of the Transnational Feminist Network	EA	M25	5	Not started	Successful delivery of the transnational feminist network
10	Activists Summer School completed	EA	M27	5	Not started	Successful delivery of the activists summer schools
11	Launch of the Project Website	VIL	M2	6	Completed	Successful launching and handling of the project website
12	Successful organisation of the kick-off Meeting	VIL	M2	7	Completed	Successful organisation and completion of the kick-off meeting
13	Project Conclusion and final review	VIL	M36	7	Not started	Successful completion of the project

Figure 8 - Screenshot of Milestones within the Project Management Tool

The File Repository of the project: It acts as the primary means of communication for the delivery and interchange of documents, dataset and multimedia contents. To reduce the number of emails among partners, and the email size, each partner is allowed to upload files, even though VIL is in charge to give

a structure to the repository. As a general principle, the documents must be uploaded to the Project Management Tool and then announced by email; this method is preferred to sending them as attachments by email.

Figure 9 - Screenshot of the File Repository within the Project Management Tool

Links: FIERCE has set up a dedicated page to concentrate the useful links, contact details and project information that all partners need. It is very useful especially to concentrate references of guidelines and relevant useful documentation.

CHAT: FIERCE has set up a chat channel. Each member can follow the evolution of the discussions in which are interested and actively participate in tasks to carry out.

Figure 10 - Screenshot of the Chat within the Project Management Tool

7.2. External communication

7.2.1. Project Website

The main communication channel between the FIERCE consortium and the external audience (academia and universities, industry and business, government and public sector, civil society and sister projects) will be the public FIERCE website that is developed and managed by ViLabs and can be accessed at <https://fierce-project.eu/>. The website contains the FIERCE overview and information about consortium. Any news relevant to the project are posted at the website automatically through the Twitter channel.

7.2.2. Scientific Publications

When one or a group of partners intend to submit for a scientific publication as part of work performed within the project, the partners should inform the Project Coordinator, the Scientific Coordinators and the consortium members before the submission, by sending an email to them with the relevant information about that publication (titles, authors, abstract). Any objection from consortium partners should be made in writing Email to the Project Coordinator and the Scientific Coordinators within seven (7) days after receipt of the notice. Example of justified objections are: (a) the objecting Party's legitimate academic or commercial interests are compromised by the publication; (b) the protection of the objecting Party's Foreground or Background is adversely affected; (c) legal, privacy, ethical constraints are not respected. Other objections could be justified. However, any objection has to include a precise request for necessary modifications. If an objection has been raised, the involved partners shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amending the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting partner shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate actions are performed following the discussion. A written acceptance shall be returned to the partner (within 2 weeks) before this partner proceeds to the submission. Moreover, the participation in exhibitions through a stand and the presentation of demos of the project results require prior agreement of the whole project Consortium. The project acknowledgment is mandatory to be included at each publication: *The present study was funded through the Project FIERCE " Feminist movements revitalizing democracy in Europe " of the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the grant agreement No 101061748.* In addition, each partner shall fill in the respective template "Dissemination Form" which is available from the Dissemination leader, at the common File repository.

7.3. Monitoring and reporting procedure

The project monitoring and reporting is performed by means of:

- Periodic physical and online consortium meetings
- Periodic reporting. It includes the following documents:
 - Periodic Progress Reports
 - Interim Progress Reports

Periodic progress Reports

Periodic Progress Reports will be produced within 30 days of the end of each reporting period. VIL will be in charge of preparing this and will ask each partner for any additional contributions. The project Coordinator will also submit it to the EC. It will include Technical and Administrative Issues:

- Research activities progress;
- Deliverables and milestones;
- Publications (Authors, title, publication, date);
- Conferences and presentations (Date, location, participants, subject, outcome).
- Effort on each Work package (PMs per WPs and months);
- Meetings (Date, location, subject, attendees);
- Travelling (Date, location, reason to travel, name of the traveller).

Progress reports will also contain the following information:

- a management-level overview of the activities carried out;
- a description of progress toward the scientific and technological objectives;
- a description of progress toward the milestones and deliverables foreseen;
- problems encountered during the project and actions taken to correct them.

Interim Progress Reports

Interim management reports (every 6 months, between the periodic reports) will be prepared for Consortium use. This report is intended for internal use and should help to detect early issues. The interim report will include the following sections:

- The key results achieved by the project during the considered period (expected contribution by Work Package Leaders);
- Financial figures summarizing the main expenses: travels, equipment, etc.)
- Effort (a table presenting the used manpower).
- Project risk summary table (table to be updated continuously by each partner and WP Leader)

The time plan for the periodic reporting is the following:

Table 12 - Periodic reporting time-plan

Report Type	Reporting Period	Submission to Coordinator
Internal Report	M1 – M7 01/09/2022 – 31/03/2023	30 days after the end of the reporting period 30/04/2023
Internal Report	M8 – M12 01/04/2023 – 31/08/2023	30 days after the end of the reporting period 30/09/2023
Official Report	M1 – M15 01/09/2022 – 30/11/2023	30 days after the end of the reporting period 31/12/2023
Internal Report	M16 – M22 01/12/2023 – 30/06/2024	30 days after the end of the reporting period 31/07/2024
Internal Report	M23 – M30 01/07/2024 – 28/02/2025	30 days after the end of the reporting period 31/03/2025
Official Report	M16 - M36 01/03/2024 – 31/08/2025	30 days after the end of the reporting period 30/09/2025

8. Planning and reporting effort and costs consumption

8.1. Planning Effort and Costs Consumption

Planning effort and cost consumption occurs through the completion of the project scheduled MS-Excel efforts and budget reports. Additionally, apart from the personnel costs that are reported as envisaged costs that may be consumed under each Task in person hours, all partners should provide a list of planned other direct costs (i.e. travel and other specific costs) for the whole project duration per reporting period. Finally, all partners should report on their average personnel rate, if the one used in the Annex 2 of the GA is no longer valid. This information is consumed by the PC to produce the Cost Baseline and Effort Schedule.

8.2. Reporting Effort and Budget Consumption

The following reports are established:

- Periodic Progress Reports (for external reporting to EC)
- Semi-annual Internal Progress Reports (internal reporting to PC)

The PC on a semi-annual basis updates internally the project progress status via the semi-annual progress reports, i.e. effort / resource consumption xlsx files received by all partners, and the activity bulleted reports provided by the WPLs.

8.3. Payments

In full line with the FIERCE Consortium Agreement and as stated under Article 7.2 the following are in action.

In particular, the Coordinator shall: notify the Party concerned promptly of the date and composition of the amount transferred to its bank account, giving the relevant references, perform diligently its tasks in the proper administration of any funds and in maintaining financial accounts, undertake to keep the Granting Authority's financial contribution to the Project separated from its normal business accounts, its own assets and property, except if the Coordinator is a Public Body or is not entitled to do so due to statutory legislation.

With reference to Article 22 of the Grant Agreement, no Party shall before the end of the Project receive more than its allocated share of the maximum grant amount less the amounts retained by the Granting Authority for the Mutual Insurance Mechanism and for the final payment.

The transfer of the initial pre-financing, the additional pre-financings (if any) and interim payments to Parties will be handled in accordance with Article 22.1. and Article 7 of the Grant Agreement following this payment schedule:

Funding of costs included in the Consortium Plan will be paid by the Coordinator to the Parties after receipt of payments from the Granting Authority in separate instalments as agreed below:

8.3.1. Pre-financing

The pre-financing payment will be the 80% of the Maximum Grant Amount, excluding the 5% of the Maximum Grant Amount will be retained by the Funding Authority from the pre-financing payment and transferred into the 'Guarantee Fund',

- **Month 1** – 1st Instalment of pre-financing: 60% of the pre-financing received will be distributed to all Partners.

- **Month 7** – 2nd Instalment of pre-financing: 20% of the pre-financing received will be distributed to all Partners, after submission to the Coordinator of the following documents:
 - Internal Financial report regarding the costs incurred in the first 7 months of the project (mid 1st reporting period).
 - Contributions required for the tasks/ deliverables that should be provided for period M1-M7 as specified in the Annex I of the Grant Agreement.
- **Month 12** – 3rd Instalment of pre-financing: 20% of the pre-financing received will be distributed to all Partners, after submission to the Coordinator of the following documents:
 - Internal Financial report regarding the costs incurred in the first 12 months of the project
 - Contributions required for the tasks/ deliverables that should be provided for period M8-M12 as specified in the Annex I of the Grant Agreement.

8.3.2. Interim Payments

Month 15 – 1st Interim payment: 100% of the first interim payment received, will be distributed to all Partners - after submission to the Coordinator of the following documents:

- The Periodic Progress Report for the M1-M15 period, containing an explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and an overview of the progress towards the objectives of the action, including milestones and deliverables identified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement.
- Individual Financial Statement for the M1-M15 period from each beneficiary and each linked third party regarding the eligible costs (actual costs, unit costs and flat-rate costs) for each budget category in accordance with Annex 4 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement. Amounts which are not declared in the individual financial statement will not be taken into account by the Commission.
- An explanation of the use of resources and the information on any subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary and from each linked third party.

Month 36 – Payment of the balance: Upon the receipt of the Payment of the balance from the EC, the 100% will be distributed to all Partners - after submission to the coordinator of the following documents:

- The Periodic Progress Report for the M16-M36 period, containing an explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and an overview of the progress towards the objectives of the action, including milestones and deliverables identified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement.
- Individual Financial Statement for the M16-M36 period from each beneficiary and each linked third party regarding the eligible costs (actual costs, unit costs and flat-rate costs) for each budget category in accordance with Annex 4 and Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement. Amounts which are not declared in the individual financial statement will not be taken into account by the Commission.
- An explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties from each beneficiary and from each linked third party.

8.3.3. Month 36 – Payment of the Guarantee Fund:

Upon the receipt of the Payment of the Guarantee Fund: from the EC, the 100% will be distributed to all Partners - after submission to the coordinator of the documents listed above.

Funding for costs accepted by the Granting Authority will be paid by the Coordinator to the Party concerned.

The Coordinator is entitled to withhold any payments due to a Party identified by the Project Plenary Board to be in breach of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement or to a Beneficiary which has not yet signed this Consortium Agreement.

The Coordinator is entitled to recover any payments already paid to a Defaulting Party except the costs already claimed by the Defaulting Party and accepted by the Granting Authority. The Coordinator is equally entitled to withhold payments to a Party when this is suggested by or agreed with the Granting Authority.

8.3.4. Procurement of Goods and Services.

KOÇ UNIVERSITY will be

- i. able to procure goods and services from third parties for the purposes of this Agreement through private procurement rules instead of the public procurement rules set forth in the Turkish Higher Education Council's Public Procurement Regulation for Higher Education Institutions Established by Foundations and the KOÇ UNIVERSITY Public Procurement Regulation, based on the exception granted under Article 44 of the KOÇ UNIVERSITY Public Procurement Regulation;*
- ii. realize procurement of goods and services from third parties as stipulated in this Agreement and the Grant Agreement, in line with best practice procurement process, equipment and asset management policies, designed to achieve value for money and have appropriate and clearly defined procedures.*

8.4. Partners efforts per Work Package

Table 13 - Partners efforts per Work Package

PARTNERS	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7
VIL	2	2	3	5	4	14	15
AAU	5	5	13	2	4	2	3
SNS	5	14	6	4	4	2	1
UCM	6	7	6	4	4	2	1
SV	4	3	3	14	6	2	1
EA	3	3	3	4	12	2	1
UG	5	5	7	4	4	2	1
AUTH	4	5	5	3	4	2	1
MI	5	4	7	4	4	2	1
KU	6	6	7	5	4	2	1
UL	13	4	7	3	4	2	1

9. Risk management

Within the FIERCE project eleven organisations from different European countries will work together following the work plan, towards the common scope to reach their common goal. In order to secure that the strategic direction, the operational management, the results and the budget of the project remain on track, the risk management is a high priority. The risk management scope is to establish processes and methods to assess and mitigate risks via an anticipatory approach.

9.1. Risk management approach

The risk management takes place through four core different stages:

- a) **Risk identification:** involves the identification of a risk
- b) **Analysis:** the assessment of risk importance
- c) **Monitoring:** continuous check of the progress
- d) **Management:** the evaluation of whether the risk level/impact is higher than the risk that could be accepted for the project

In case that a risk exceeds the acceptable levels, a risk analysis activity will be instantiated that will define the required actions in order to set the risk within acceptable levels. In addition, the management of risks involves the planning of contingency actions, the redistribution of resources, the evaluation of the results, as well as ensuring the stability of the new status.

9.2. Risk management roles and responsibilities

The responsible persons for FIERCE are the Project Coordinator and the Quality manager with the active support of the Scientific Coordinators. Their main obligation is to identify, monitor, and handle internal and external risks and inform all (or directly involved) partners when necessary. At the level of risk identification, the WP leaders play an important key role to communicate with the Coordinator any upcoming risk they foresee. On a bi-weekly basis, the consortium meets online and WP leaders are expected to present the progress and achievements of their WP, as well as an assessment of risks that may hinder progress and propose contingency plans where necessary to address any specific identified risks.

In particular, the types of risks that may emerge in a project like FIERCE fall into the following categories:

- **Operational risks:** The WP Leaders along with the project Coordinator should identify as early as possible any barriers to be overcome in order to meet the WP objectives, the activities required to overcome these barriers, the personnel allocations which will provide the right competencies to perform the tasks and the time / budget allocation rules which allow to reach the intermediate objectives.
- **Time risks:** In terms of deadlines, it is important that the project follow the work plan, therefore the WP Leaders together with the Coordinator should identify early in advance any schedule change or delay in producing the expected deliverables and the impact of such a delay on the overall progress of the project; the organisational and budget changes which may be necessary to catch up on delays.

- **Competence risks:** Partners should identify as early as possible the required personnel with the relevant expertise to perform the tasks as well as the possible conflicting demands for the required personnel within each organization.
- **Force majeure risks:** In the case of force majeure, the project Coordinator should identify any risks with the WP Leaders, define mitigation plans according to the EU and project country laws, and communicate that with the Project Officer and Policy Officer (especially in case of political issues).

9.3. Risk management process

All the identified risks are incorporated into a Risk Log File, which is also available online at the Project Management Tool. The risks will be maintained as permanent registers (never deleted) in order to provide a complete, accurate and updated view of all the incurred risks of the project (irrespective of whether or not they have already been solved).

The risks are duly characterized by:

- Risk number
- Responsible partner (the partner responsible for its resolution and follow-up)
- Description (textual),
- Impact/risk level (high, medium, low)
- Likelihood (unlikely, likely, very likely),
- Situation (inactive, pending, solved),
- Proactive measures
- Action (adopted countermeasures or remedial actions).

9.4. Potential risks

This is the current updated list of risks has already been identified at the Grand Agreement. This list will be further extended as the project progresses.

Table 14 - FIERCE Project Risks

Description of risk (Low/Medium/High)	WPs	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
Engaging the target groups in replying to the questionnaires (Low)	All WPs	The project must ensure the accessibility of the questionnaires and dissemination activities to support such actions, while asking for preventive authorisations.
Delays to deliver the information needed for other WPs (Medium)	All WPs	Proper planning of work with milestones and alternative plans in case deviations from the plan occur. Increase the communication among WPLs from biweekly to weekly. Additional personnel will be employed when this issue will be identified.
Low cooperation with the necessary local actors in each country (medium)	WP2, WP3,	The project must ensure the accessibility to the local networks and the proper dissemination among the

	WP4, WP5	stakeholders and the target groups, to support project's activities
Conflicts among partners arise (low)	All WPs	The coordinator will mediate to find a consensual solution and, in case of no solution, take a binding decision.
Legal issues arise (low)	All WPs	The coordinator will contact the legal experts of the European Commission to solve the issue.
Transnational network: Difficulty to network and do peer reviews due to differences in the democratic initiatives and language issues (low)	WP4, WP5	The selection of projects for the FIERCE Actions will have to take into consideration capacity and willingness of actors to involve in peer reviews and networking activities. Language capacity of actors and ability to communicate will also be part of selection criterion.
Low integration of results of WP4, WP5 in to results of WP1,2,3 because of timing and other research constraints (Medium)	All WP	Projects partners' meetings and constant communication will be a key in ensuring that the more research-oriented packages and more practice oriented one are integrated. Researchers from WP1,2,3 will have to be participating in key stages of WP4 and 5. Mitigation: Regular communication between partners, and All partners are involved in selection committee for cascade funding
Communication difficulties at local level towards feminist groups and actors not fluent in English (Medium)	WP4	Mitigation: policy recommendation toolkit will include a translation of executive summary in all languages of the project. All Partners will be involved in communicating and spreading interim and results of the project in local/national languages.
Limited access to potential interviewees, feminist, and anti-feminist (Low)	WP1, WP2	The project members must collaborate across cases to exploit different entry points into the interview pool and heavily utilize snowballing where necessary.
Possible reluctance of anti-gender protagonists to be willing to give interviews(Low)	WP4	We have the expertise and experience in conducting interviews, handling and safeguarding personal data and information in a way to make sure any risk for participants in our study is limited to an absolute minimum.

10. Annexes

10.1. Annex 1 – peer Review report template

 Funded by the European Union	
 FIERCE <i>Feminist movements revitalizing Democracy in Europe.</i>	
Project Acronym	FIERCE
Project Name	Feminist Movements Revitalizing Democracy in Europe
Project Number	101061748
Topic	HORIZON-CL2-2021-DEMOCRACY-01-03
Type of Action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting Authority	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date	1 September 2022
Project end date	31 August 2024
Project duration	36 months

Internal Review

Deliverable title
WPx-title

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the European Research Executive Agency can be held responsible for them.

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Internal review, Dx.x: Title Page 2 of 3
 Document Information

Deliverable Number and Name	
Work Package No	
Due Date (month)	
Submission Date (month)	
Lead Beneficiary	
Version	
Author name(s)	
Contributor(s)	
Reviewer(s)	
Keywords	
Type	R – Document, report or ETHICS
Dissemination level	PU – Public or SEN – Sensitive

Evaluation: Please rate the quality of the deliverable on a scale from 1 to 5. (1:poor, 2:below average, 3:average, 4:good, 5:excellent)

Criterion	Grade	Comment
Technical/Scientific value		
Structure		
Clarity		
Relevance to objectives ¹		

Major strengths and/or weaknesses: (Please explain briefly)

¹ The reviewer should consult the description of the respective Work Package, as included in the Technical Annex.

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Internal review, Dx.x: Title

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Recommendations:

Deliverable has sufficient quality as is²:	
Deliverable needs minor re-writing (please specify):	
Deliverable needs major re-writing (please specify):	

Comments & Suggestions:

#	Description of proposed change	Importance ³ (E HR R)
1		
2		
3		

Next steps:

Is it necessary for the revised deliverables to be reviewed again before submission?	(Yes/No)
---	-----------------

[Date]

[Reviewer's Name, Organisation, Affiliation]

² The current version of the deliverable is ready for submission.

³ The reviewer should indicate the significance of the proposed change with regards to the overall quality of the deliverable. Proposed values include: E (essential), HR (Highly Recommended), R (Recommended).